

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *CITRULLUS COLOCYNTHIS*,
SCHRADER. PART I. EXAMINATION OF THE OIL*

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The seeds contain 21% of a pale brownish yellow oil with a bitter taste. The oil contains oleic, linoleic, myristic, palmitic and stearic acids and a phytosterol (m. p. 122-25°; acetate, m. p. 109-10°).

The seeds of Colocynth or "Bitter apple" (*Kadakavade Kayi*) are obtained from *Citrullus colocynthis*. It is a vine of the gourd family (N. O. Cucurbitaceae), native to the warmer parts of Persia, Arabia, Syria and the African and European shores of the Mediterranean. It is also cultivated in Spain and Cyprus. The plant grows wildly in the North-West, the Punjab, Sind, Central and Southern India. The fruits resemble oranges in appearance with yellow and green stripes (A. F. Hill, "Economic Botany", p. 271).

Colocynth has been used medicinally for a very long time in Greek, Arabian and Indian medicine and it enters into many of the purgative pills of modern pharmacy in the form of solid extract.

The internal pulp of the dried peeled fruit is found to be useful in constipation, hepatic and abdominal, visceral and also cerebral congestions, dropsy etc; and the root in jaundice, ascites, urinary diseases, rheumatism, biliousness, constipation, fever and worms etc. The juice of the fruit mixed with sugar is a household remedy in dropsy. The oil from the seeds is used for snake-bites, scorpion-stings, any bowel complaints, epilepsy and also for the growth and blackening of hair (Nadkarni, "Indian Materia Medica"; Chopra, "Indigenous Drugs of India", pp. 121-123).

The earlier investigators (Walz, *N. Jahrb. Pharm.*, 1858, 9, 16, 225, Henke, *Arch. Pharm*, 1883, 221, 200; Johannson, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1885, 24, 154; Naylor and Chappel, *Pharm. J.*, 1907, 79, 117; Grimmaldi and Prussia, *Bull. chim. Pharm.*, 1909, 48, 93; Power and Moore, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 99; David, *Pharm. Ztg.*, 1928, 78, 525; Rozsa, *Ber. Ugar. Pharm.*, 1928, 4, 196; Chopra *et al*, *Ind. J. Méd. Res.*, 1929, 18, Jan.; "Indigenous Drugs of India", 1933, pp. 121-123; Agarwal and Dutt, *Curr. Sci.*, 1934, 3, 250). have all worked mostly on the pulp of the fruit excepting Grimmaldi and Prussia and Power and Moore who have done some work on the physical constants of the oil.

In view of the day to day use of the Colocynth seeds in the local veterinary medicine and the deficiency of our knowledge respecting their constituents, it seemed desirable to subject them to a more thorough chemical examination.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The seeds used for the present investigation were collected from a region near about Kurnool town in Madras Presidency.

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The crushed seeds (100 g.) were extracted with the following solvents successively in a soxhlet and the extracts were dried at 100°.

TABLE I

Solvent,	Extract,
Petroleum ether (b. p. 30°-60°)	20.95%
Ethyl ether	2.30
Chloroform	0.29
Ethyl acetate	0.41
Ethyl alcohol	2.62
Total 26.57%	

The petroleum ether extract gave a pale, brownish yellow oil with a bitter taste. The other extracts consist of highly colored and viscous materials about which no definite conclusions could be drawn.

Fatty Oil

The fatty oil was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-60°) and the purified material had the following constants.

TABLE II

	The present authors.	Power and Moore.	Grimmaldi and Prussia.
Ref. index	1.4725 (28°)	—	—
Sp. gravity	0.9257 (28°)	0.9273 (20°)	0.9289 (15°)
Acid value	3.97	—	—
Sapon. value	174.0	186.7	191.7
Iodine value	117.8	126.6	120.7
Reichert-Meißl value	0.3510	—	—
Acetyl value	17.9240	—	—
Hehner value	91.64%.	—	50.72%.
Unsapon. matter	2.4%	—	—

Mixed Fatty Acids

The oil (500 g.) was saponified and the resulting hard soap was powdered and extracted with ether in a soxhlet apparatus to obtain the unsaponifiable matter. The residual soap powder was freed from ether and the fatty acids were liberated and purified. The mixed free fatty acids were found to have the following constants: mixed fatty acids, 91.0; mean mol. wt. of the mixed acids, 279.45; iodine value, (Hanus), 121.0.

About 300 g. of the mixed fatty acids were separated into their saturated and unsaturated components by Twitchell's lead-salt-alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921,

18, 806). During the course of separation, a brown, resinous, semi-solid material, which was insoluble even in boiling alcohol, remained stuck to the bottom of the flask. The liberated saturated and unsaturated acids had the following constants.

TABLE III

	Saturated acids.	Unsaturated acids.
Per cent.	72.12	27.88
Mean mol. wt.	267.3	289.4
Iodine value (Hanus)	4.879	132.0

Liquid Fatty Acids

A portion of the liquid acids was brominated according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils and Fats", 6th Ed., Vol. I, p. 585). A white crystalline solid, tetrabromostearic acid (m.p. 113-114°; M.W. 597.5) was obtained, indicating the presence of linoleic acid in the liquid acid mixture. From the filtrate no hexabromostearic acid could be isolated.

Another portion of the liquid acid mixture was oxidised by cold 1% alkaline potassium permanganate solution according to the method of Lapworth and Mottram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628). From the mixture of hydroxy-acids, thus obtained, the following were isolated.

TABLE IV

Acid.	M.p.	M.W. (found).	M.W. (calc.)
Dihydroxystearic acid	135°	315.0	316.4 (oleic)
Tetrahydroxystearic acid	167-68°	347.2	348.4 (linoleic)

Thus, the presence of oleic and linoleic acids among the unsaturated acid mixture was established.

Solid Fatty Acids

The mixture of solid acids was esterified with methyl alcohol in the usual manner and 40 g. of the saturated methyl esters were fractionally distilled at a pressure of 5 mm.

Fraction No.	Temp. range.	Wt.	M.W. of acids.	Fraction No.	Temp. range.	Wt.	M.W. of acids.
I	below 165°	3.4 g.	225.4	VI	182°-185°	8.6 g.	282.2
II	165°-170°	1.0	251.4	VII	185°-187°	2.7	284.5
III	170°-175°	4.6	256.7	VIII	187°-188°	2.5	285.2
IV	175°-180°	4.2	259.2	IX	above 188° (residue)	7.9	292.3
V	180°-182°	5.1	271.2	Total		40.0	

Fraction I.—The crude acid from this fraction after repeated crystallisations from 80% alcohol gave an acid melting at 50-51°, with a molecular weight of 226.7, identified as myristic acid. A mixed melting point determination with a laboratory sample of myristic acid did not change the melting point.

Fraction II-IV.—The acids liberated from these fractions after repeated crystallisations from 80% alcohol yielded pure palmitic acid (m.p. 60-61°, M. W. 256.4). Mixed with pure palmitic acid, the melting point remained unchanged.

Fraction V.—This gave an acid which corresponded to an eutectic mixture of palmitic and stearic acids. Repeated crystallisations from various solvents gave a product melting at 56-57° (M.W. 267).

Fraction VI-IX.—The acids liberated from these fractions after repeated crystallisations from 92% alcohol gave pure stearic acid (m.p. 69-70°, M.W. 283.6). The melting point remained unchanged on mixing this acid with pure stearic acid.

Thus the saturated acids were found to consist of myristic, palmitic and stearic acids.

Unaponifiable Matter

This was mostly an oily mass with a small quantity of fine crystals interspersed in it. From the ether extract of the unaponifiable matter, a phytosterol (m. p. 122-25°) was obtained in a colorless and pure state after repeated treatment with animal charcoal and recrystallisations from 75% alcohol. This compound gave all the characteristic colour tests of phytosterols. Its acetate melted at 109-110°.

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